

The Impact of Talent Management on Performance: Moderating Effect of Career Management

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Abstract: Talent managements emphasizes on talent which is defined as a high performance with developed skills. The research will address approaches implemented in talent management across different countries in the world, and then will address studies implemented in the Middle East, and at last the research will provide a detailed case study in Lebanon about the impact of talent management on employees' performance. The quantitative methodology will be implemented for data collection of 100 respondents to study the impact of talent management on employees' performance. Retention and talent management will be the independent variables as for performance will be the dependent variable. The results proved that the higher the talent management programs are implemented the higher the retention rate will be and the higher the performance will be.

Keyword: Talent Management. Performance, Career

Introduction

In the late nineties, the study of McKinsey "War of talent" has generated the concept of talent management which consisted of giving importance to retain qualified and talented people in order to succeed in business (Berger, 2019).

Competitive advantage and sustaining organizational performance are one of the most important sources formed by human capital. Talent management should be implemented and developed by companies in order to recruit and retain employees.

According to Best (2018), talent management plays a crucial role in filling the gap between the required talents and the current ones in order to accomplish their objectives. Talent management practices were stated by Bhatia (2019) to be conducted at all employee's lifecycle phases starting from the first day an employee is hired until the day he quit the company.

Furthermore, it was indicated by (Billings, 2020) that in order to implement human resources' vision, possessing qualified workforce with high skills and competencies form talent management.

Many authors have developed definitions and terms of the term "talent management" and (Billsberry, 2018) state that they can be classified into three categories. The first one defines talent management as the selection, training and planning of employees which constitute the elements of a human resources team. The second one focuses on a pool of qualified people as a set of procedures established by an organization to provide a sufficient flow of employees in the company. The third talent management's type emphasizes on talent which is defined as a high performance with developed skills.

The research will address approaches implemented in talent management across different countries in the world, and then will address studies implemented in the Middle East, and at last the research will provide a detailed case study in Lebanon about the impact of talent management on employees' performance.

Talent Management

It was indicated by Blass (2009) in their research that two types of results were in the core of the talent management literature review: the organizational level and the individual one. In the first type of results, it was proposed by the literature that talent management affects the results of a company such as improving effectiveness, ensuring progress and competitive advantage in addition to ROE and ROI that form the financial effects of a company (Blaxter, 2018). The literature suggested that talent management has also results at the individual level and motivation and commitment are the most introduced strategical ones to gain high organizational performance (Bluen, 2013). A diversity was revealed by dimensions' scholars in identifying the practices of talent management from different point of views. Three categories of talent management practices such as the staff recruitment, training and employee's retention were presented and are the most applied in the companies. On the other hand, the following talent management dimensions such as attraction, retaining and motivating qualified people were addressed (Bolarinwa, 2015) and will be employed in this study because of the real meaning of talent management practices as follows: organizations were given the most talented and attracted employees in order to reduce costs while achieving a better result. Moreover, in addition to the cost of dismissing a wrong employee and the cost of hiring a new one, bad hiring procedures can be costly and vary from 20% to 200% of the annual salary.

Attraction is defined (Bond, 2017) as the procedure of producing candidates and helping to build the employer's image. Finding appropriate candidates is the basis of recruitment process to meet organizational expectations in an efficient way. He stated that the following procedures such as

determining the job vacancies, the sourcing strategy and the recruitment policy are included in an efficient recruitment process. Job vacancies in companies start when a new unit is opened or when employees leave the company. Two strategies of internally and externally outsourcing exist and it is important to internally fill vacancies because it has a positive impact on institutions.

The recruitment policy contains three principal policies regarding the decisions about sourcing, the level of flexibility in responding to recruitment requirements and the relationship between recruitment and other policies such as the reward one.

Moreover, the purpose of publishing an information within certain conditions is to describe the job offer and attracting a high number of talented candidates in addition to communicating a good brand of the companies' products and adapting to the employment rules and regulations. Processing and evaluating applications also involve examining and compare carefully and take decision regarding the recruitment of a candidate based on the results of the application. However, the final task in the recruitment process is about notifying the candidates who either have passed successfully or failed in the recruitment tests and interviews.

The impact of employees' engagement on both performance and retention is important to talent motivation. Productivity can be improved as well as turnover decreased by motivation's application. A considerable amount of money is spent by many companies to motivate their employees using a big range of policies. For instance, motivational speakers are hired by some companies in order to inspire employees and fees up to \$50,000 are required by "motivational coaches" (Brant, 2018). An internal force making human beings to behave in a wide range of ways defines motivation and therefore is vital for understanding human's personality.

Talent development is crucial for both companies and individuals since qualified employees can contribute in enhancing the organizational competitiveness and increase the capacity of adapting to changing environment. The development concept is different from the training one. Employees can be trained to respond to clients' requests, to enter data in a system or to drive a truck. Nevertheless, according to Brewerton (2016), a bigger challenge is formed by the development in topics like judgement, responsibility, communication and decision making.

Training and Development

Ability is defined according to AMO Model and to Bryson. (2011), as the potential to perform the given work activities and as the human resources management which are related to the necessary competencies that should be implemented successfully at workplace.

The human resources management literature suggests a lot of examples of inadequate human resources management abilities of employees and its detrimental effects.

It is argued by Fandale et al. (2010) that employee's qualifications and competencies in human resources practices are insufficient. They also said that employees' effectiveness will undoubtedly be affected by a lack of training thus diminishing the overall effectiveness of companies. It will be impossible for any organization to implement human resource practices in an efficient way if someone does not possess the necessary skills. Bullock. (2013) state that the other dimension of ability in Talent

management is “an individual’s ability to build and sustain relationships and networks.” Leaders are the people who are capable to identify hidden talent among their subordinates.

Companies must offer employees suitable opportunities even if they are capable to follow the human resources policies in order to benefit from their talent (Cappelli, 2014). First of all, a good support for the human resources professionals is needed. Secondly, adequate capacity is necessary in terms of time to get involved in human resource implementation. Third, the definition and the distribution of roles is important as well as minimizing role’s ambiguity; rules and regulations should be consequently supportive. Nevertheless, talented employees are not always provided by human resource professionals with the services that they need because there is not enough time for them to be advised by human resource experts who are not able to provide effective support. Additionally, they hesitate in abandoning their remaining responsibilities in order to play a new organizational role in supporting line managers (Chapman et al. 2019).

In such a context, the talented employees should develop their personal chances in order to demonstrate their skills. Furthermore, providing ample opportunities for their followers is also part of a leader’s job to display their potential. Finally, Charan et al. (2019) shows in his research that human resource management unit is sometimes unable to define adequate opportunities for the qualified employees, so their real talent is not exhibited. Therefore, a good human resource policy is essential for providing clear opportunities to distinguished employees.

Organizational Performance

Organizational performance plays a major role to companies in order to succeed in the competitive business field nowadays and because of that constitutes an important of the studies’ interests (Cheese, 2020).

A group of task-oriented employees form an organization which purpose is to achieve a common target by continuously coping with the quickly internally and externally changing environment. On the other hand, performance is known as a measurable result of the achievement level of the companies’ targets (Chew, 2019).

Organizational performance is defined by Sastry (1997) as combining both organizational effectiveness and efficiency. The external indicators utilized to assess the services of a firm are described as an organizational effectiveness (Chiboiwa, 2018) while the way methods are employed in the production of services is referred to organizational efficiency.

It is argued by Storey(2019) that organizational performance measurement can be considered as contemporary performance measurement while financial measures such as ROI and profits are emphasized by the traditional one. Both financial and non-financial performance measures however are used by contemporary performance measurement in the organizational strategy.

Using financial performance measurement has been claimed by many authors to not be enough to assess a company’s performance. It was indicated by Sun (2017) that financial performance measurement is not enough nowadays to evaluate the performance of an institution in an uncertain business environment.

Financial perspective: providing an indication such as profitability, revenue growth and asset utilization regarding the final outcomes of the companies is the objective of this perspective. It also emphasizes the importance of client satisfaction, enhances items and other services.

Internal business processes perspective: the purpose of this perspective is to identify the main series actions that a company must take in order to improve the value of the products and deliver them to customers and shareholders in a right manner. These actions constitute product development, production, manufacturing, delivery and post sale services.

Learning and growth perspective: Facilitating the other three dimensions of the Balanced Scorecard by filling the gaps between employee skills, information systems, and the workplace requirements is the purpose of this perspective which indicators include employee skills, job satisfaction and availability of information.

Figure 1 Corporation Mission

Source Poley: 2012

The effects of talent management practices on companies have been studied by many researchers in the past years. These effects have been classified by Takeuchi (2019) based on the perspective of different studies into two groups. Talent management is claimed by the first one to have an indirect positive impact on organizational performance by improving human resources practices (Thang, 2018) while talent management is argued by the second group to have a direct impact on the whole organizational performance. It can be concluded therefore that talent management through the attraction and retention of talented people improves organizational performance.

Employee Engagement

An interest in employee's commitment has raised in the past because of the role it plays in companies to help them gain competitive advantage. Firms are supported by employee engagement in creating a healthy work environment which in return helps in increasing performance and productivity (Truss, 2005).

Need-satisfying approach: it is suggested by Truss (2019) that employee engagement has three types which are physical, emotional and cognitive and are influenced by three states which are: meaningfulness, safety and availability.

Burnout-Antithesis Approach: According to Truss (2016), employee engagement is considered to be the opposite of the burnout-antithesis's elements which are exhaustion, cynicism and inefficiency. Workload, supervision, rewards and recognition, social support and perceived fairness are six dimensions by which the previous mentioned elements happen.

Talent Management and Performance

Nowadays, companies face the challenge of selecting and retaining talents within a period of time. According to Wayne (2017), the definition of talent management is the management of the entire workforce from the attraction of talented employees, to their promotion and finally to find a successor after they retire.

Identifying the gaps between the talent in place and the one required to drive a successful business is included in this process. In addition to that, the result of ensuring the right person in the right job is part of talent management. The recognition of talented employees within a company is to develop them and afterwards to conduct development activities for the talent pool in order to retain employees.

It is stated according to Wright (2015) that talent management is the institutional mind-set which aimed based on the business' goals, to make sure that the number of talents is available to find the right people to the right job at the right time.

It was revealed that during the recruitment process, companies hire talents which skills match the organization's ones in both the short and long run. It was claimed by many studies that implementing talent management in an efficient way will help to improve the rate of employee's recruitment and retention.

The researches of Xanthopoulou (2019) regarding talent management strategies and employee commitment showed that an efficient talent management planning, regular support from leaders, balance between work and life and environmental factors are necessary to retain talented employees to the company.

The use of technology is important in all the stages of talent management practices as it was indicated by Yalabik (2018) during the start-up stage of a company. In a competitive environmental business, the presence of social media is crucial to attract and hire potential talented candidates.

It was suggested by researchers to explore the main areas serving for future development in which competency model tailored to business was recommended by them. Additionally, technology is used when it comes to conduct talent review based on their performance.

A study done by Youndt (2016) revealed that the process of talent management will be enhanced by an effective implementation of its strategy which will improve the quality of the recruitment process and also retention's rate. Financial performance is closely related to these findings.

The strategy of an enterprise relates to talent management. Barney has stated in 1991 that the resources based on the view of the company is the foundation of the strategical role of human resources. It was concluded by him that the resources are scarce, inimitable and non-substitutable and thus can be a source of competitive advantage leading to a more strategical research recognizing the human capital's role.

According to (Best, 2018), it is essential that employees are told by the strategical firm how the company is clearly separated from the competition. Employee's actions will not be guided by an abstract and a vague strategy. Moreover, the objectives of a company are stated in a clear way that they can be measured and that employees' role in accomplishing their objectives are well understood.

According to Becker, Huselid and Beatty (2009), it was contended that strategy is set by companies and not by individuals, because it is meant that differentiation from competitors is needed to every company through its strategy in order to survive.

Therefore, it is argued that employees should be made by the companies into an instrument to implement the strategy which also should be distinguished from its competitors in order to be prosperous. The creation of a distinguished workforce strategy is labeled as the way of working with the human capital.

The firm is not differentiated from its competitors in the first phase but rather is implementing its most suitable practices which are related to its business. A "bare minimum" effort's level is represented for the company, since a minimum of effort that companies do not move more slowly than others is assured but the firm is put at risk since the most adequate practices are not difficult to imitate.

A generic is represented in the second phase where the first steps of aligning the labor force with the strategy of the company are taken into consideration. In this phase, a generic differentiated workforce has been adopted by the firm to their specific strategy which is still easy to copy by the competitors and therefore a sustainable competitive advantage will not be led.

In the third phase, the company is differentiating its personnel through its critical capacities. Strategic capacities are the job process, which are necessary to the enterprises, and the competitive advantage is provided to the firm in comparison to its opponents. A choice is important to be made which abilities are essential since the strategic practices are the driven factor for the company's performance and will result in an unequal return if invested in.

In the last phase, a more important knowledge of the important abilities of the company is taken into account, where the differentiated labor force is achieved on a job-level. All jobs are not necessary

differentiated for companies which rather may have simultaneously different responsibilities in all four types. Nevertheless, it is necessary to differentiate strategical jobs.

It is written by Michael Porter that an organization can find a better technology in accomplishing a task than its competitors and by that gaining a competitive advantage. Becker, Huselid and Beatty noted that the corporate actions which are crucial to the company's strategy and which offer a competitive advantage to her are considered as strategical efficiencies.

They argue that the labor force can turn into a competitive advantage by choosing a distinguished workforce strategy. Nevertheless, it is noted that there is an increase between the strategical abilities identification of a company and the creation of a differentiated personnel strategy due to an absence of link that the company often should have to express how talent can lead to a strategical successful capacity.

Balanced Scorecard concept contains the strategy map which describes the strategic objectives as part of strategic drivers' chain based on a logical cause and effect. The workforce dimension of the company's strategy is highlighted by talent map and according to Billings (2020), the learning and development is opposed to the base line in the talent map which include the talent drivers of the firm.

H1: There is a significant effect between talent management and performance

Implementation of a successful talent management and performance

It has been shown by researches that successful talent management organizations have installed an internal consistent system and strengthen the practices used in order to attract, select, assess and retain talent. Furthermore, these practices are aligned with their business strategy, organizational culture and long term objectives (Blass, 2019).

Additionally, there are many owners in the company who are the Chief executive officer, the managers at every level and the human resources department. The Boston Consulting Group, BCG and WFPMA argue as well that it is not sufficient for the talent management to be successful to implement management practices in a linear fashion way, because each activity is to be accomplished in parallel and since the logic that lies behind talent management is incorporated into the managerial culture.

The report from Capability to Profitability by the Boston Consulting Group (2012) denotes that firms which have the best economic performance strongly exceed their peers in three domains which are talent management, performance management, rewards and leadership development.

Moreover, it was found that incentives are used by these organizations to engage a strategic position. Strategic effect is a high performance variability talent and is not easy to attract and retain. Talent is more largely defined by potential in order to create wealthy managers and to reinforce their increased potentials and attracting simultaneously internationals.

H2: There is a significant relationship between the successful implementation of talent management and organizational performance

Career management planning and organizational performance

Weber founded the concept of bureaucratic institutions which states that the former organizational career consists of employees' promotion. Since the career's management responsibility has switched from the employer to the employee, there were needs of changing the structure of companies and improving technologies (Billings, 2020). These changes have led during last three decades to a non-linearity in the career models which became less predictable.

It was stated that the past organizational career disappeared due to the environmental changes and the new tendency of focusing on people as employability instead of employment safety. Future employees would rather have less boundaries careers in which they are personally responsible to manage it and they would be disengaged from employers.

This resulted in the concept of the multifaceted career which is a career where the knowledge, the skills and the competencies are reshaped by the individual to fit a changing work context and employability is seek to be maintained, in addition to the flexibility in values and a constant learning process accompanied by intrinsic rewards (Bhatia, 2019).

Nevertheless, Bhatia (2019) found that despite rumors of its death, organizational career is still desired by today's employees. It is proposed by her that a new institutional career be a mixture of the former bureaucratic career and a new one without boundaries. Employees' expectations are needed to be acknowledged while satisfying the needs of a company is important to retain qualified people.

Furthermore in the new organizational career, horizontal moves are important in the same way as vertical ones which will contribute to lateral tasks, variety of skills, innovation and cross-training.

He also asserted that the evaluation of a new organizational career is in terms of both subjective and objective success' measurements. There will be equity in rewards and a successful lateral move within the company since it has been known till now to move vertically in the firm. The career will consequently be forced into more of a "spiral" evolution instead of a solely linear one.

The definition of succession planning, or succession management according to (Huang, 2001) is the process of providing an adequate supply for present and future key jobs successors.

The projection of the competence needs for the future for some specific positions is involved in the succession planning since employees' evaluation which are on the "short-list" for these positions and a plan for how to improve their skills is implemented in order to present the strategical interests of the company (Billsberry, 2018).

Complicated social systems such as companies are managed by values-based management. The way organizations perceive and evaluate themselves has been changed by this kind of management. Bureaucratic control has been criticized to lead to ineffectiveness and counter productivity due to the simplification of the complexity of companies into financial measures which do not facilitate an analysis of several stakeholders and their values

The way companies interpret strategic issues, decisions and changes is affected by values and management decision-making is influenced by them. Employee behavior's is based on values and will not be strategic unless these values are provided to them with guidance in a strategical way.

H3: There is direct relationship between career management planning and organizational performance

Talent development and organizational performance

Garavan, Carbery and Rock (2012) define talent management as “a meaningful under-developed and under-researched concept”. Nevertheless, it is stated that since a talent in another company is not needed in our ones, that's why it seems that a lot of people agree that talents be developed in house instead of hiring them from outside the company.

It is contended according to Burkus and Osula (2011) that a deliberate practice opportunities should be created by the company and that all employees should have access to training programs. Four future main areas in the field of talent development are presented by Garavan, Carbery and Rock (2012) such as:

Focusing in strategic talent and integrate talent development processes with the strategy of business

Since not all the practices are efficient, it is recommended to differentiate talent development

The responsibility and supervision over talent development is shifted from the company to individuals who will be able to manage their development which in return will add more values to practices as a mean of training people in different contexts

Talent development process is always proposed due to a constant demand for talent development integrated with the need for a combined strategy which composes different sources of learning along the lines of the 70-20-10 model.

According to (Becker, Huselid, & Beatty, 2009), seventy per cent of this learning model are based on work, twenty per cent on coaching and guiding and ten per cent on official training programs.

The following figure describes the general development tools which is a collection performed by the researchers of this study. The model mentioned above can be used in the following way where the work based on learning constitutes 70% of the model, the networks and relationships 20% and the courses 10% of the model.

The 70 %: work-based learning and internal movement

The work-based element is the most important development. It is noted by Garavan, Carbery and Rock (2012) that in order to have an efficient work-based learning, three elements are necessary and are detailed as follows:

Unstable tasks should be comprised in the job description

Employees should leave their comfort zones

A wide strategic component is required thus involving contact with different directors is necessary

It is suggested by Wikström in the (2013) that a senior colleague could teach employees which can also learn by taking part in the work of colleagues. Employees are given the opportunity to expand by offering them special tasks or by leading projects that contribute to change the company or help personal to work in cross-functional teams.

Additionally, many ways of changing the environment at workplace are reflected by temporary job positions and providing employees with challenges in different services and different units is also important.

The purpose of networks and relationships with people from inside or outside the company is to develop employees by putting them in contact with other ones, whether they are directors or colleagues from the same department. Due to the knowledge of today's driven economy, competitiveness requires working with cross-functional teams in addition to clients or products focus business units approach used by companies.

According to Wenger (2006), these types of organization are useful but the so called communities of practices which are groups of people that share a common interest or knowledge can complement such forms of organization. Stories are shared in the community of practices which could be for example a line of profession.

A problem is solved by committed participants and their knowledge mapped during the discussions. Driving strategy, generating new business lines, promoting the spread of most adequate practices, developing professional skills constitute the objectives for companies to administer communities of practices and retain their talents. Shaw and Fairhurst (2008) suggest that the mentoring relationship

could be achieved through communities of practices in order to engage employees. Matters of common interest are discussed by employees and their peers.

The development of mapping of competencies which is fundamental for an employee to be successful in performing any given task at a certain point of time represents the definition of competency mapping. It is becoming primordial to develop competitive advantages within the company in a modern challenging business environment (Sanghi, 2007). The body of any successful business activity depends on employees' competencies or skills.

Over the past, there has been a lot of discussions regarding business strategies and importance of having competencies in order to survive in the market.

Competency mapping leads to employee's job satisfaction improvement and also increase the rate of retention. This is also useful for a company in managing its recruitment process, improving its performance management and determining which are the best training for employees.

H4: There is direct relationship between training and development and organizational performance

Data Collection

The main aim behind every research is to collect data through the use of a survey or questionnaire to be able to validate the research hypotheses and solve the research problem proposed. Furthermore, the data that will be collected will be analyzed using the SPSS statistical package and this will be done throughout the construction of the survey based on the research variables which are the dependent and independent variables.

As proposed previously, the main objective which lies behind the research design is to study the correlation among talent management, retention and their impact on employees' performance as a whole. Furthermore, to measure employees' performance, there will be many indicators including the absenteeism rate, and the turnover rate. The questionnaire will be constructed based on Likert Scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree).

Sampling

The sample will include a defined number of contributors which will respond to the constructed questionnaires to study the impact of talent management on employees' performance. The questionnaire will be constructed based on the dependent and independent variables.

The sample will target contributors which work in different banks, and a survey will be distributed for data collection among different contributors which occupy different positions in different banks.

Variables Characteristics

Understanding the relationship between the research variables is the main objective which lies behind this research. The independent variables are employee retention and talent management practices as for the dependent variable is the performance of the employees in the workplace.

Furthermore, the research will study how each variable affect the employees performance, and whether it affects it positively or negatively. Accordingly, we had previously proposed our three hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: There is a direct relationship between talent management and employees performance

Hypothesis 2: There is a direct relationship between employee retention and employees performance

Independent Variable Measurement Scale

The independent variable can be defined as the factor which has a direct effect on the dependent variable. It is the core of every research and based on them the questionnaire is constructed. However, the independent variables of the research will be addressed briefly through this section of the research

Talent Management: it is the act of managing potential employees in the workplace to enhance employees' performance and by that boosting the productivity as a whole. This can be done through engaging employees in daily activities and in taking decisions. Another act of talent management is conducting periodic training and development programs to upgrade the employees' skills and ensure career growth on the long run. Thus, the higher the talent management practices are implemented in the workplace, the higher the performance will be reflecting better productivity.

Retention: is defined as the act of retaining employees in the workplace and minimizing turnover rate. This can be achieved throughout implementing many strategies and talent management programs. Implementing such programs can lead to enhancing career growths and to the satisfaction of the employees' needs.

Dependent Variable Measurement Scale

The dependent variable in this research is employee performance, and it will be measured throughout constructing a set of questionnaires which tend to indicate the employee performance in the organization. Several indicators will be constructed including absenteeism rate, job satisfaction, and motivation and performance appraisals.

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.998 ^a	.995	.995	.00223

a. Predictors: (Constant), Talent Management Average, Retention Average

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.000	.001		-.859	.393
	Retention Average	.473	.057	.458	8.277	.000
	Talent Management Average	.552	.056	.542	9.788	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance Average

The significance level showed a level of 0.00 for retention with respect to performance and a level of 0.00 for talent management with respect to performance meaning that the null hypotheses is rejected, and the alternative hypotheses is accepted.

Based on the mentioned statistics, the below hypotheses can be validated:

- There relationship between retention and performance is accepted
- There is relationship between talent management and performance is accepted.

Pearson Correlations

		Performance Average
Talent Management	Pearson Correlation	.996**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	100
Retention	Pearson Correlation	.995**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	100

The mentioned table explains briefly the relationship between the research variables and whether this relation is positive or negative based on an indicator called Pearson Coefficient. However, the results will be addressed as follows:

- Positive relationship between talent management and performance (0.996)
- Positive relationship between retention and performance (0.995)

Validity and Reliability

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.998	3

The validity and reliability analysis aims to study whether the collected data are valid or not based on an indicator called Cronbach Alpha. The indicator showed a sign above 0.7 which means the collected data are valid and ready for statistical analysis.

Conclusion

At last, the research findings proved that effective global talent management requires a formal succession planning system since the purpose of the development programs is to identify employees considered as important assets to the company from whom it is expected to move on higher positions in the long run. Similarly, development programs should be integrated with succession planning systems.

The necessity of having a formal succession planning system is combined with different human resources processes. Talent development is also asserted to be too risky since conditions are constantly changing in a modern business world. A talent management doctrine inspired by supply chain management should instead be adopted by organizations.

However, the research also found that there is positive relationship between retention, talent management and employee's performance and the results were validated using the regression analysis and the Pearson Correlations.

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